

THE NEED TO STUDY THE PRE-COMPETITIVE ACTIVITIES, KURDISH FIGHTERS

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Annotation. In this article, the author interprets the opinions of wrestlers about the scientific research of competitive activity. The analysis of competitive activity and its detailed study is reflected as one of the important tasks facing coaches and specialists. The opinions of a number of specialists and scientists were studied, and conclusions were developed to solve.

Аннотация. Мазкур мақолада курашчилар мусобақа фаолиятини илмий тадқиқ этиш борасидаги фикрлар муаллиф нуқтаи-назари бўйича талқин қилинган. Мусобақа фаолиятини таҳлил қилиш ва уни атрофлича ўрганиш мураббийлар ва мутахассислар олдида турувчи муҳим вазифалардан бири сифатида ўз аксини топган. Бир қатор мутахассислар ва олимларнинг фикр ва мулоҳазалари ўрганилган, муаммоларни хал этиш бўйича хулосалар ишлаб чиқилган.

Аннотация. В данной статье с точки зрения автора интерпретируются мнения борцов о научном исследовании соревновательной деятельности. Анализ соревновательной деятельности и ее детальное изучение отражается как одна из важных задач, стоящих перед тренерами, специалистами. Были изучены мнения ряда специалистов и ученых, разработаны выводы для решения поставленных задач.

Keyword. Sports, wrestling, competitive activities, indicators, technical and tactical skills, method of improving the combination actions of wrestlers, planning.

Таянч сўзлар. Спорт, кураш, мусобақа фаолияти, кўрсаткичлар, техник-тактик маҳорат, курашчиларнинг комбнацион харакатларини такомиллаштириш усулиёти,режалаштириш.

Ключевые слова. Спорт, борьба, соревновательная деятельность, показатели, технико-тактическое мастерство, методика совершенствования комбинационных действий борцов, планирование.

INTRODUCTION

Today, special attention is paid to the development of physical education and sports in our country. Because today's Uzbek sport is considered an integral part of our national culture, it remains one of the main tools in educating the broad masses of people in a high moral spirit and strengthening their health [1].

Relevance. The problem of researching competition activities in sports has become an integral part of modern sports theory. Without competitions and competitions, the sport does not have its essence. Most scientific literature on the topic states that research on competition activities is important in the effective management of the training system. Today, the implicit concept of "competition activity" has become an integral part of sports theory and sports competition theory. The relevance of the chosen research topic is due to the growth of

competition in wrestling, which requires the search for reserves to increase the level of special strength training of wrestlers, including improving the educational system [2].

Continuous search and generalization of innovative solutions is necessary to develop scientifically based training content and methods of improving strength training of athletes at different stages of training. At the same time, the qualities of strength are in complex interdependence on the development of other physical qualities and the level of technical and tactical readiness. There is an opinion that in order to optimally build strength training of wrestlers, it is enough to identify muscle groups in which the sleeve is much needed in competition activities [Boyko, Danko 2004]. Therefore, the assessment of the level of strength training of wrestlers depends on the strength indicators of these muscle groups. The main content of the strength training of wrestlers is an increase in special speed and strength training, which is traditionally grasped by the dynamics of the main wrestling movements with an appropriate imitation close to the amplitude, speed and strength indicators, and the superior use of special exercises. Accordingly, the main means of training wrestlers with strength will be exercises for eating their own weight and partner's weight, exercises with weights and resistance, exercises on trainers and in the mannequin. Each group of exercises eat specific advantages and disadvantages for training wrestlers.

It is believed that you can establish the advantages of simulators yourself range of movements, quantifying the loads and clearly affecting certain muscle groups. B. M. The results of ribalko's research allow us to believe that neither working on projektil Gymnastics and simulators, on the realization of the potential of winning strength, can replace the struggle on the mat. Years of coaching experience also shows that high results in the development of special strength qualities can only be achieved when using the optimal ratio of basic and special tools and the appropriate type of power training concept [9].

G. S. Considering the power training system of wrestlers, Tumanyan notes that " one of the main ways to develop maximum strength is through exercises performed in the 80-90% range of a single repetition maximum (TM) " [Tumanyan 2001]. This growth mechanism is known as V. N. Well explained by Platonov:

"...the increase in strength is associated with an improvement in neuroregulatory mechanisms and an increase in the capacity, strength and mobility of the alactate mechanism to provide muscle contraction with yenergy "[Platonov 1997: 21]. The method of large loadings is in demand in the training of qualified wrestlers, since it does not eat associated with the growth of muscle mass.

For this reason, leading experts and scientists pay special attention to the issue of "preparatory-competition" affiliation. These points in turn indicate the relevance of the issue chosen by us as the topic of the article.

A number of R & D studies have been carried out by leading sports wrestling experts on the research of competition activities. In this place is R.A.Pilayan, Ya.K.Koblev, Yu.A.Shakhmuradov, J.M.Nurshin, K.S.Sariev, M.Yu.The research work of scientists such as Inyakin is of particular importance [10].

It should be noted that in Uzbekistan, this issue has not been ignored by experts. A.Q.Atoev F.A.Kerimov, R.D.Halmukhammedov, A.N.Abdiev, scientists such as unicorns have done significant work on improving the scientific and methodological foundations of training.

Foreign scientists (Segedi I., Franchini E., Sterkowicz S, Miarka B. et al.) of particular importance is the research of the activities of the competition of unicorns. Scientific and

pedagogical observations conducted in recent years show that the issue of training wrestlers is directly related to the features of competition activities.

As the purpose of the article, it was determined to highlight the need and importance of wrestlers to research the activities of the competition. In the coverage of this issue, special scientific and methodological literature on the topic was analyzed, the tasks of the wrestlers were carried out to monitor the competition's foliations, to study the opinions of coaches and athletes.

For a long time in the theory and methodology of sports training, the ways and means of training athletes have been modernized in different ways, separated from the practice of competition for a certain period of time.

This is due to the peculiarity of the conditions of competition activity, the specific state of the athlete within the framework of competitions, the difficulty of accessing unbiased information about the dynamics of body functions that are being analyzed during the competition. Competition practice has a significant impact on the athlete's body. This is often due to the fact that it is extremely extreme activity (showing the maximum value of endurance and strength;

maximum performance and speed of movements, coordination accuracy and complexity of movements, etc.). The presence of a stressful character of nervous and emotional tension, etc. So, in particular, as a component of sports activities, the struggle of single struggles in competitions is officially the final stage from Logic positions, reflecting their extra-curricular activities and the results of educational activities in addition to training[8].

In fact, the practice of competition is primary, making specific demands on wrestlers, determining the vector of their activity in future training.

Training program for improving combinatorial movements of wrestlers.

In the study of the topic of the article, research methods of literature analysis, pedagogical observation, theoretical analysis and generalization were applied. The results of the analysis of special scientific literature, the study of the advanced practical experience of leading specialists, the study of the level of technical and tactical training, the analysis of competitive activities, the study of the relationship between the level of technical training and the parameters of physical fitness became the basis for the development of a training program for

When developing programs, it is necessary to take into account the increased readiness and the fact that in modern struggle with competition loadings requires an optimal level of technical readiness from athletes.

The technique is aimed at increasing the ability of athletes to prepare for competitions and show tactical actions in turn, educating the combined nature of taknik.

The program would last 3 months, divided into three phases, with each phase being thirty days long. Training was conducted from January 2019 to March 2019. Each stage was given ten days (15 minutes each) aimed at combining movements in training. In each of them, combination methods were used (1.scheme). In addition, at each stage, ten days (15 minutes) were allocated to perform combinatorial actions with a resistance of 50% and 100% according to this scheme. Of course, here, first of all, the task of learning and developing skills in the performance of combinatorial actions, and then resisting is considered.

Комбинацион методларни бажариш дастури Схема № 1.

№	Таркиблар	Юкламаларнинг давомилиги дақиқаларда	январь	февраль	март
1	Икки энгидан ушлаган ҳолдаелкадан ошириб улоқтиришлар. Алдамчи ҳаракатлар; 1. Ичкаридан оёқ тагидан 2. Орқадан чалиш 3. Ташқаридан оёқ юзаси билан илдириш	150'	150'	-	-
2	Ҳимоя 1.Тирсакларни кўкракка қисиб олиш. 2.Рақибга ён билан бурилиб,озроқ тиззаларни букиб пасайиш. 3.Рақибнинг орқасига ўтиб олиш.	150'	150'	-	-
3	Қарши усуллар 1.Ёндан супуриш. 2.Орқадан чалиш.	150'	-	150'	-
4	Бардор усулларидаги ҳаракатлар: 1. Рақибга яқинлашиб, қоматни пасайтириб уни кўкракка зич сиқиш ва орқага қайтариш. 2. Орқага қайшишни давом этириб, рақибни ўзига қисган ҳолда оёқларини гиламдан узиш, орқага йикила бошлаб, рақибни елкалари билан гиламга ташлаш билан бурилиш.	150'	-	150'	-
5	Алдамчи ҳаракатлар; Белдан ошириб ташлаш.	150'	-	-	150'
6	Қарши усуллар 1. Ичкаридан оёқ тагидан супуриш. 2. болдир билан ташқаридан	150'	-	-	150'

	хар ҳил номдаги оёқнинг тагдан илдириш.				
7	Оёқ устидан оширб орқага йиқитиш Алдамчи ҳаракатлар; 1. Белан оширб ташлаш 2. Орқадан чалиш 3. Олдиндан чалиш	150'	150'	-	-
8	Ҳимоя 1.Рақибни ужум қилган томондан қарш томонга чекниш ва оғирлк марказнинг шу томонга ўтказиш ва усул охирига етиш пайтида, курашчнинг ўзини босиб қолиш. 2.Рақибга кўкрак билан буриш ва ҳужумдаги оёқни орқароққа олиш. 3.Олдинга эгилиш ва ҳужумдаги оёғини орқага қолдириш.	150'	-	150'	-
9	Қарши усуллар 1.Ичкаридан қошша қилиш 2.Ичкаридан оёқ тагидан супуриш.	150'	-	-	150'
10	Рақиб мувозанатини ҳужумдаги оёғингиз томонга йўналтира бориб, бироз қайшган ҳолда ҳужумчи оёқни рақиб оёғи орасига ўтгазиб уни қўймаслик усулини ўнг ва чап томонга бариш.	150'	-	-	150'
Жами:		1500'	450'	450'	650''

The results obtained and their discussion.

Observations and analysis on the topic show that wrestlers show that competition activities are an integral part of the immediate preparation process. The generalization of information in several publications on the topic, the study of the opinions of coaches and athletes on this topic, and the direct observation of competitions (on the scale of the city, region and Republic) fully confirm the importance of comprehensive study of competition activities[12].

As a result of observations and analyzes, it was determined that in the course of the competition, a variety of technical and tactical actions are carried out by the athlete. This

aspect makes the issue of research of competition activities sufficiently complex. The level of skill and state of readiness of wrestlers makes it possible to effectively apply methods (or technical actions) [4,5,6,7].

It is known that several changes are taking place in the modern era of the development of sports wrestling, in particular, such as Greco-Roman, wrestling, judo, sambo. This includes changes in the timing of the competition, the age indicators of athletes and new approaches to training athletes, of course. Changes such as the above have a significant impact on wrestlers' competition activities, natural. In turn, the change in the activities of the competition creates the need to organize the training of wrestlers at the level of the requirements of the activities of the competition.

Progress in sports also led to an increase in the number of competitions. Not only in wrestling, but also in other sports, there has been an increase in the number of competitions in recent years.

According to the data in the literature, the number of annual competitions in the mobayan 1980-1990 was 10-15 in fencing, 20-25 in freestyle wrestling, 10-15 in wrestling and judo, while the number of competitions in the period 1991-2000 was 20-25, 25-30 and 20-25, respectively. At the same time, it was determined by experts that the time to engage in the annual preparation process also increased. During the annual preparation, it was indicated that the training time increased from 800-1000 hours in several sports (1980-1991) to 1000-1200 hours (1991-2000). From the above information, it can be seen that the activities of the competition of wrestlers are inextricably linked with the planning of their mashugulot process [8]. As the number of competitions increases, the time spent on the preparation process also increases.

The problem of researching the activities of the competition remains relevant even in today's periods of the development of sports wrestling. The results of a large number of research works and research of specialists in this place confirm our opinion [13].

Conclusion. Observations and analyzes carried out by us have shown that in the system of training wrestlers, the analysis of competitions is important. The need and importance of researching competition activities can be described as follows.

1. Research of the activities of the competition allows you to determine the current state of the athlete, his shortcomings and achievements.
2. Research of competition activities strong athletes determine the prospects for the development and preparation process of the competition activity Model[11].
3. Increases the Skill, Competition opportunity and experience of the athlete.

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